

DIFFERENTIATED METHODS OF GENERAL AND SPECIAL TRAINING OF YOUNG ROAD CYCLISTS AT THE INITIAL STAGE OF SPECIALIZATION

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ABSTRACT

The article presents a methodology for the expediency of constructing the dynamics of training and competitive loads in the process of training cyclists of primary sports specialization at the age of 13-14, both for the conditions of sports training and for competitions.

Key words: cycling, young cyclists, loads, stage of sports specialization.

During the short historical period of independence of the Republic, significant events took place in the country's sports movement. Uzbekistan was one of the first to adopt (Decrees of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 271 of 05/27/1999 "On measures for the further development of physical culture and sports in Uzbekistan" and No. 371 of October 31, 2002 "On the organization of the activities of the fund for the development of children's sports in Uzbekistan") and others. At the same time, important tasks are set for the further improvement of higher sports skills and the conquest of leading positions by Uzbek athletes in the international sports arena (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 9, 2017 No. PP-2821 "On the preparation of athletes of Uzbekistan for the XXXII Olympic and XVI Paralympic Games of 2020 in the city of Tokyo (Japan)", including cycling.

This article is presented on the basis of the conducted studies of the feasibility of constructing the dynamics of training and competitive loads in the process of training cyclists of initial sports specialization at the age of 13-14, both for the conditions of sports training and for competitions. According to the existing calendar of mass sports competitions of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the calendar of the International Cyclists Union, which is the **relevance of the selected work study**.

The aim of the research is to optimize the training methodology for cyclists of initial specialization based on the intensification of the educational and training process and the decrease in the amplitude of fluctuations in the level of the volume of the competitive and special training load in the annual cycle.

In accordance with the purpose of the study, we have defined the tasks:

1. To determine the effectiveness of the variant of training cyclists with a reduced amplitude of fluctuations of the competitive and training load in combination with an increased volume of exercises performed with increased intensity during a one-year training cycle.

2. To develop methods for a comprehensive assessment of the signs of the physical condition of young cyclists at the stage of sports specialization and to study the influence of physical condition data on the sports results of young road cyclists.

3. Experimentally substantiate the influence of multidirectional trained load on the indicators of special and functional readiness of road cyclists at the age of 13-14.

The study revealed the structure of the distinctive anthropometric features of road racers. Methods for a comprehensive assessment of signs of physical condition have been substantiated. The prognostic capabilities and significance of these methods in the diagnosis of giftedness in the conditions of a youth sports school have been determined.

Achievement of the training effect due to the use of the original variant of constructing the annual cycle of training cyclists, on the basis of "leveling" the volume of special training loads in combination with their intensification is shown. The widespread opinion about the harmfulness of early achievement of sports form was not confirmed. [4] In the tested version, cyclists covering 18-20 thousand kilometers in a year achieved high sports results during seven months of the competitive period.

Based on the tasks set, a range of research methods were determined, such as analysis of domestic and foreign literature and data from sports practice; pedagogical observation; timing and testing of training and competitive loads according to heart rate monitoring data; methods of testing and control exercises, competitions; pedagogical experiment; methods of mathematical statistics.

The research was carried out in the conditions of the educational-training process of initial sports specialization groups (13-14 years old) in several stages.

Thus, the optimized technique made it possible to reveal the effect of training in cyclists, where significant functional changes are observed, leading to an economy of physiological processes and increasing the stability of the body's activity when working in a state of fatigue. [3] In view of the fact that the level of functional adaptive mechanisms must be taken into account in the complex assessment of the signs of physical condition, on the basis of which the selection of athletes in adolescence can be carried out.

Three leading analyzers for cyclists were selected for research: vestibular, visual and receptor (motor). An experimental and a control group of 15 athletes were organized, approximately at the same age (13-14 and 14-15 years old) and physical fitness. (table 1)

Table 1

Annual training plan for 13-14 years old cyclists of the first stage and first year of training

Content	Training periods and months												Total hours
	transition		preparatory				competitive						
	X	XI	XII	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VII I	IX	
The number of hours devoted to theoretical studies	-	-	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	12
	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	2
Physical Culture and sport; their effect on the athlete's body													
The regime and nutrition of athletes	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	2
Cycling Basics	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2
Equipment and inventory	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
Rules of the competition	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	2
Traffic rules and road signs	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	1	-	3
Amount of practical knowledge	16	15	14	1	15	19	15	17	30	31	29	17	237
Practice as an instructor and assistant in refereeing (judge)	-	1	-	9	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	4
Studying the technical equipment of the bicycle and its repair	1	-	1	1	-	1	1	1	-	1	1	1	9
The number of GPP and TFP	1	-	-	1	1	1	-	-	-	1	1	1	7
SP	1	-	-	1	1	1	1	2	3	3	3	1	17
Teaching technique, tactics and motor skills:	8	10	7	1	9	10	5	4	9	9	7	4	94
	5	4	6	2	4	6	8	9	17	17	17	9	106
- the number of training sessions	24	30	21	3	27	30	12	12	28	28	22	12	282
	15	12	18	6	12	18	27	27	50	50	50	27	318

for general physical training and physical fitness SP	160	130	130	1	130	250	500	700	100	100	100	600	5700
- the number of training hours by: GPP and TFP	50	40	80	0	40	160	360	550	0	0	0	340	3890
SP	60	50	50	0	85	85	45	30	800	730	690	160	1055
- total number of km (transmission no more than 77.6 dm): Highway Cross Track	40	40	-	5	-	-	65	80	100	160	180	90	455
- the number of competitive exercises, km				0	5	0			40	30	70		
Total hours	10	-	-	-	5	5	30	40	60	80	60	10	
Total kilometers													300
													612
													5700

It was expressed in an increase in the level of physical performance, maximum oxygen consumption, in a decrease in heart rate, pulmonary ventilation, oxygen demand and debt when performing standard bicycle ergometric loads.

The parameters determined by us - the rudder amplitude and oscillation, [1] decided that the rudder oscillation amplitude in the control and experimental groups before vestibular stimulation is at relatively the same damage, and after vestibular stimulation in both groups, the rudder oscillation amplitude increases. In the same state, the rudder oscillation amplitude also increases after the application of metered loads. And the steering oscillation is reduced. [2]

As a consequence of the experimentally substantiated technique, it can be concluded that with the help of the technique for determining the rudder oscillation and the frequency of its oscillations, the most stable state of the analyzer systems was found, mainly at a driving speed of 30-50 km per hour. The lowest stability of the analyzer systems was noted at a driving speed of up to 20 km / h and above 50 km / h. [5]

As a result of the comparative analysis, it seems important to draw the following conclusions that the modified training methodology provided a significantly higher (in

comparison with the effect of the generally accepted methodology) development of the body's functional capabilities and improvement of special physical qualities of cyclists in the experimental group, which is confirmed by the dynamic growth of their sports results.

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